

FAPESP funded-research and public policies: Connections for achieving the SDGs

Ana Carolina Spatti¹, Adriana Bin², Evandro Coggo Cristofolletti³, Matheus Leite Campos⁴,
Yohanna Juk⁵, Karen E. F. Pinto⁶

¹*spatti@unicamp.br*, ²*adribin@unicamp.br*

University of Campinas, School of Applied Science, Pedro Zaccaria Street, 1300, Limeira – SP, (Brazil)

³*evcoggo@unicamp.br*, ⁴*matleite@unicamp.br*, ⁵*yjuk@unicamp.br*, ⁶*karenefp@unicamp.br*

University of Campinas, Institute of Geosciences, Rua Carlos Gomes, 250, Campinas – SP, (Brazil)

Abstract

There is a growing concern about generating and measuring research impacts beyond the scientific dimension. It is important to understand how knowledge translates into social impact, contributes to public policy, and addresses the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). The SDGs require action from various stakeholders, including the research community, with funding agencies playing a significant role. This paper aims to identify and characterize the impact of research funded by FAPESP (São Paulo Research Foundation), the largest state research funding agency in Brazil, on public policies related to the SDGs. We utilized secondary data from the Overton and Dimensions platforms to establish the connection between science, policy, and the SDGs. Preliminary results indicate that out of 25,492 articles supported by FAPESP between 2020 and 2021, only 101 (0.37%) are referenced in policy documents (217), related to 15 of the 17 SDGs. One of the key contributions of this research is to demonstrate the political impact of FAPESP-funded research, which can serve as a form of accountability towards different stakeholders and advocate for the effects of investing in social-oriented research.

Introduction

The generation and recognition of the research impacts beyond the scientific dimension is a topic that has gained substantial attention and recognition in recent decades. On the one hand, there are growing efforts to understand the different forms of knowledge production and how research can generate impacts on the social, cultural, economic, and political dimensions. On the other, there are also specific demands for research to contribute to achieving the SDGs, relying on public policies and government programs to achieve socially relevant and politically determined goals as a path for action. This need becomes even more relevant when considering the global challenges at the 27th United Nations Climate Conference (UN/COP 27). Thus, it is essential to understand the impact of scientific research on public policies and its contributions to meeting social demands and global challenges (Bornmann et al., 2022), which includes, precisely, climate change and social inclusion, materialized in the SDGs of the UN Agenda 2030 for global development (UN, 2015).

According to Wang & Barabási (2021), the most significant impact of studying the science of science is its implications on policies since this connection considers the assumption that policymakers and impact decision-making can exploit critical scientific findings. Such studies belong to social impact measurements in Scientometrics (Tahamtan & Bornmann, 2020).

Citations of science in policy documents can occur for different reasons, including (i) instrumental uses (knowledge applied directly to solve problems); (ii) conceptual uses (research influences or informs how policymakers think); and (iii) tactical uses (citing research to support or challenge an idea) (Yin et al., 2021). Capturing this impact on policy has significant potential benefits, including showing the relevance of research in real-world settings (Vilkins & Grant, 2017). However, this understanding still needs to be improved (CNPq, 2012). There need to be more studies that discuss the organizational conditions necessary for the manifestation of impact from the perspective of users, whether policymakers or other social actors (Yin et al.,

2021; Edler et al., 2022). With this in mind, we aim to explore the impacts of research funded by the São Paulo Research Foundation (FAPESP) on public policies and its contributions to achieving the SDGs. FAPESP is Brazil's largest state research funding agency, accounting for almost 40% of the state's total annual financial support for research activities. Our study was guided by and aimed to answer the following research question: how and to what extent does FAPESP-funded research impact the formulation, implementation, and evaluation of public policies to achieve the SDGs?

Funding agencies are essential players in the research landscape, able to dictate agendas and influence research communities through their programs and resources. They are also pressured to justify and legitimize research spending. For those reasons, understanding the impact of funded research also becomes imperative for this type of organization. Funding agencies have the potential to enhance this impact. FAPESP is a public foundation supported by the taxpayers of São Paulo, with the mission to support research projects in higher education and research institutions in all fields of knowledge. It is one of the leading funding agencies in Brazil.

In this sense, the study can contribute to discussing sustainability from a policy perspective. Moreover, it gives substance to the theoretical and practical discussion about the relationships between science, public policies, and SDGs in an emerging economy context.

Data and methodology

In order to explore the science-policy-SDG relationship, we applied secondary data from the Dimensions and Overton platforms. The Overton database tracks scientific research (here represented by the output of scientific articles) to policy documents in more than 180 countries. When comparing the policy components from Dimensions and Altmetric databases, Overton has four times more publication citations in policy documents, tracked in about 15% more sources (according to data available for 2021 on the Overton.io website).

In turn, the Dimensions database integrates data and analysis tools based on artificial intelligence technologies that allow broad coverage of global academic production and some of its main qualitative effects. Therefore, Dimensions enables analysis of content not covered by traditional databases and platforms, such as datasets, grants, and clinical trials. A recent study (Singh et al., 2021) indicates that the Web of Science, Scopus, and Dimensions databases have significantly different journal coverage, with Dimensions being the most extensive. Specifically, it features about 80% more journals than Web of Science and 50% more journals than Scopus.

The methodological approach was divided into sequential steps:

- (i) We identified the total number of scientific articles supported by FAPESP in the Dimensions database. Considering the timeframe 2020-2021, we found 25,492 outputs.
- (ii) We calculated the share of articles (0,37%) mentioned in policy documents from Overton.
- (iii) We analyzed the results by characterizing the articles and policy documents by citing country, organization type, and SDGs.

Preliminary results

In total, 25,492 articles published between 2020 and 2021 had FAPESP as its research funder. According to Overton data, 0.37% of this set was mentioned in policy documents (Table 1).

Table 1. Number of publications related to policy (2020, 2021)

<i>Publications</i>	#	%
No. of scholarly output funded by FAPESP citing policy documents	101	0,39
No. of policy documents citing scholarly output funded by FAPESP	217	-
No. of scholarly output funded by FAPESP	25,492	100%

Source: Based on Dimensions and Overton data.

The most cited scientific publication in policy documents received 36 mentions from international organizations such as research centers, health agencies, and development banks. The article, published in The Lancet Journal, discusses the resurgence of COVID-19 in Manaus, Brazil.

The 217 policy documents are primarily from intergovernmental organizations (IGOs) (43%) (Table 2). The United States is the second leading source, representing 10% of policy documents that mention FAPESP-funded articles. In comparison, Brazil represents less than 1%, with two articles cited by the Igarapé Institute and the Applied Economic Research Institute (IPEA). The corresponding policy documents deal with illegal mining in the Amazon and the Brazilian agricultural census.

Table 2. Countries of policy documents that cite FAPESP-funded publications

<i>Country</i>	<i># Policy Documents</i>	<i>%</i>
Italy	1	0,5%
Malaysia	1	0,5%
Norway	1	0,5%
Singapore	1	0,5%
South Africa	1	0,5%
Brazil	2	0,9%
Finland	2	0,9%
India	2	0,9%
Mexico	2	0,9%
Netherlands	2	0,9%
Philippines	2	0,9%
Austria	4	1,8%
Sweden	4	1,8%

Belgium	5	2,3%
Canada	5	2,3%
Germany	5	2,3%
Switzerland	12	5,5%
France	14	6,5%
EU	16	7,4%
UK	20	9,2%
USA	22	10,1%
IGO	93	42,9%
Total	217	100%

Source: Based on Overton data.

Regarding the type of organization, 38% are government institutions, 43% IGOs, and 18% are think tanks (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Policy document organization type

Source: Based on Overton data.

Of the 217 policy documents, 38 (17.5%) are related to SDG 15, 29 (13.4%) to SDG 11, 22 (10.1%) to SDG 10, and 20 (9.2%) to SDG 13 (Figure 2). The 4 SDGs represent more than half of the policy documents, thus highlighting connections to "Life on Land", "Sustainable Cities and Communities", "Reduced Inequalities", and "Climate Action". However, SDG 4, i.e., "Quality education", and SDG 17, "Partnerships for the goals", were not identified.

Figure 2. Relationship between policy documents that cite FAPESP-funded publications and the SDGs

Source: Based on Overton data.

Final remarks

The findings suggest that the overall impact of FAPESP-funded research on policy documents is limited, with only a small percentage of the research being mentioned. One significant observation is the geographic bias in the policy documents. The majority of these documents come from international organizations and the United States, while Brazil has minimal representation. This discrepancy indicates a potential gap in translating research into domestic policy actions.

Furthermore, the study highlights the lack of diverse organizational engagement in utilizing FAPESP-funded research. Government institutions and intergovernmental organizations are the main users, while think tanks and non-governmental actors have limited involvement. This calls for greater collaboration with diverse stakeholders to enhance the policy impact of research and ensure a more comprehensive approach to addressing global challenges.

The concentration of policy documents around certain SDGs, such as Life on Land, Sustainable Cities and Communities, Reduced Inequalities, and Climate Action, is noteworthy. However, the absence of policy documents related to Quality Education and Partnerships for the Goals raises concerns about the comprehensiveness and balanced focus on all SDGs, which calls for a holistic approach and attention to all goal areas.

To gain a deeper understanding, it is crucial to conduct further investigation that explores the mechanisms through which research influences policy-making, identifies barriers and facilitators, and incorporates the perspectives of policymakers and other stakeholders. This will enable a more comprehensive assessment of FAPESP's funding strategies and their effectiveness in achieving social impact and contributing to the SDGs.

Although our results bring some insights into the scientific influence on public policies, we are yet to verify the level of this influence in implementing and evaluating such policies. These caveats define the challenge for the next steps of our research. We intend to apply text mining

techniques in order to identify if the scientific knowledge is being applied directly to solve problems (instrumental use), to inform policymakers (conceptual use), or to support an idea (tactical use). Furthermore, we are currently widening our sample, encompassing articles published from 2015 – the year the SDGs were approved – to 2022. Such a step will enable us to identify the emergence of other SDGs and possibly assess if they were also affected by the recent government transition in Brazil.

Our study has many relevant implications for policy and research-making. It emphasizes the need for FAPESP and other funding agencies to critically evaluate their strategies to enhance the impact of research on policy formulation, implementation, and evaluation. It is essential to comprehend the influences of scientific knowledge on the different stages of the public policy cycle. Such understanding may support research efforts toward sustainable development by emphasizing the ties between science and politics, seeking synergies between research and political agendas, and reinforcing the inextricable connection between science and society.

Acknowledgment

We gratefully acknowledge support from FAPESP under Award Number 2021/15091-8 and 2021/00508-0. The findings and results are solely the responsibility of the authors.

References

- Bornmann, L., Haunschild, R., Boyack, K., Marx, W., & Minx, J. C. (2022). How relevant is climate change research for climate change policy? An empirical analysis based on Overton data. arXiv:2203.05358.
- Conselho Nacional de Desenvolvimento Científico e Tecnológico (CNPq), Usando a Ciência como Evidência em Políticas Públicas (National Academies Press, 2012).
- Edler, J., Karaulova, M., & Barker, K. Sianes, A., Vega-Muñoz, A., Tirado-Valencia, P., & Ariza-Montes, A. (2022). Understanding conceptual impact of scientific knowledge: the Sustainable Development Goals on the academic research agenda. A scientometric analysis. *PLOS ONE*, 17(3): e0265409.
- Tahamtan, I., & Bornmann, L. (2020). Altmetrics and societal impact measurements: Match or mismatch? A literature review. *El Profesional de la Información*, 29(1), e290102.
- United Nations (2015). Transforming our World: The 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development. Outcome Document for the UN Summit to Adopt the Post-2015 Development Agenda: Draft for Adoption. New York.
- Vilkins, S., & Grant, W. J. (2017). Types of evidence cited in Australian Government publications. *Scientometrics*, 113(3), 1681-1695. doi: 10.1007/s11192-017-2544-2.
- Wang, D., & Barabási, A. L. (2021). *The science of science*. Cambridge University Press.
- Yin, Y., Gao, J., Jones, B. F., & Wang, D. S. (2021). Coevolution of policy and science during the pandemic. *Science*, 371(6525), 128-130. doi: 10.1126/science.abe3084.